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Sr.	Title	Source	Subjects	Broad Category	Publisher	ISSN	E-ISSN	Country	
6083	BHU Journal of Communication Studies	UNIV	Communication; Media Technology; Tourism, Leisure and Hospitality Management	Arts & Humanities	Deptt. of Journalism and Mass Communication, BHU	22315578		India	N a
5467	Journalism and Mass Communication	UNIV	English;Media Technology	Arts & Humanities	David Publisher	21606579		United States	N a
5054	Mass communicator	UNIV	Communication; Media Technology	Arts & Humanities; Multidisciplinary		09739688	0973967x	India	N a
5083	mass media	UNIV	Media Technology	Arts & Humanities		2277-284		India	N a
344	Massachusetts Review	Scopus	Arts and Humanities	Arts & Humanities	Univ Massachusetts Massachusetts Review	00254878		United States	
5646	Novoe Literaturnoe Obozrenie	UNIV	Linguistics and Language	Arts & Humanities	Federal Agency for Press and Mass Communciation	08696365		Russia	N a
4935	Pragyaan: Journal of Mass Communication	UNIV	Media Technology	Arts & Humanities		09745521		India	N a
5060	Review of Journalism & Mass Communication	UNIV	Communication; Media Technology	Arts & Humanities		23335742	2333573	United States	N a
3478	Transactions of the Charles S. Peirce Society	Scopus	Arts and Humanities	Social Science; Arts & Humanities	University of Massachusetts	00091774		United States	